

that of groundnut cake because gingelly seeds have about 10 mg iron per 100 g compared to that in groundnut seeds, 2 mg per 100 g^{1,6} (Table 1).

TABLE 4—VOLUME SUSCEPTIBILITIES OF OIL CAKES AND OIL SEEDS

Material	10 ⁻⁶ (Volume susceptibility at 10 kG)			
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
Groundnut cake	1.358	1.145	2.255	2.212
Gingelly cake	8.05	7.643	6.821	5.481
Groundnut seed			-0.109*	
Gingelly seed			-0.080*	

*Mean of ten trials.

Another possible explanation for the paramagnetic behaviour of an oilcake may lie in assuming the formation of paramagnetic centres during crushing. The nature of such changes occurring during crushing is not clear. A paramagnetic metal ion present in the seed may be complexed by the fibrous proteins such that the paramagnetic character of the ion is quenched. In the cake, this situation might change involving the destruction of the complex leading to the 'liberation' of the metal ion. Filing and breaking of the horn were shown to produce, by esr studies, free radicals due to molecular chain breaking which is analogous to the present observation⁷.

The magnitude of the volume susceptibility of a particular cake appears to be influenced by the amount of residual oil in it. The more 'dry' is the cake containing less oil, more is the susceptibility.

Samples of a cake obtained from various sources did not have the same value of magnetic susceptibility. This might be due to different degrees of crushing in various mills. Rice and its flour showed diamagnetic susceptibility of the same magnitude. A similar observation was made with wheat and its flour. This rules out any metal contamination during crushing in the mill. Hence, the paramagnetic behaviour of oil cakes may be due to some structural transformations in the constituents of the seeds during the crushing process. Further work is in progress with a view to understanding this phenomenon.

References

1. Y. G. DEOSTAHLE, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 988.
2. K. A. WILLIAMS, "Oils Fats and Fatty Acids", 4th. ed., J. A. Churchill Ltd., 1960.
3. H. G. KRISCHENBAUER, "Fats and Oils—An Outline of Their Chemistry and Technology", 2nd. ed., Reinhold, New York, 1960.
4. L. V. COCKS and C. VAN REDE, "Laboratory Handbook for Oils and Fats Analysis", Academic Press, New York, 1966.
5. L. F. BATES, "Modern Magnetism", 4th. ed., Cambridge University Press, 1963, p. 115.
6. *The Wealth of India*, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1972, Vol. 9, p. 286.
7. H. M. ASSENHEIM, "Introduction to ESR", Hilger Watts Ltd., London, 1966, p. 155.

Synthesis of Some Thiazole Substituted Phenylimino-4-thiazolidinones

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones^{1,2} and in view of their pharmacological activities³, the syntheses of the title compounds have been made in our present study.

In the present investigation unsymmetrical thiocarbamides (2) were synthesised by condensing 2-substituted amino-4-(4'-aminophenyl)thiazoles (1)⁴ with arylisothiocyanates. The thiocarbamides were condensed with chloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in glacial acetic acid to furnish the thiazolidinones. There was possibility of formation of two products, 3a and 3b. Tlc study indicated the presence of only one product. The authenticity of the compound was further confirmed by the chemical method. When the product, obtained by the condensation of *N*²-*p*-(2'-anilinothiazol-4'-yl)phenyl-*N*²-phenylthiocarbamide and chloroacetic acid, was hydrolysed with alcoholic hydrochloric acid, the filtrate after separation of thiazolidione (m.p. 200°), on basification gave 2-anilino-4-(4'-aminophenyl)thiazole (m.p. 139°). The m.p.s., agreed with the reported values^{4,5}. Similarly, the structures of other thiazolidinones were chemically confirmed. There is formation of thiazolidione and aminophenylthiazoles in each case. This supports the structure 3a for the 4-thiazolidinones.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded in nujol mull on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The pmr spectra were studied in CDCl₃ on a Varian T-60 spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard.

*Synthesis of N*²-[*p*-(2-anilinothiazol-4'-yl)phenyl]-*N*²-phenylthiocarbamide 2 (as representative case): A solution of 2-anilino-4-(4'-aminophenyl)thiazole (0.01 mol, 2.67 g) and phenylisothiocyanate (0.012 mol, 1.62 g) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 h. After cooling, the crystalline thiocarbamide was filtered and dried. It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 220°. Similarly, other thiocarbamides were prepared and their characterisations are recorded in Table 1; ν_{max} 1215-1250 (C=S stretching), 3150-3300 (NH stretching), 1560-1580 cm⁻¹ (NH bending) and characteristic absorptions of thiazole ring.

Synthesis of 2-p-(2'-phenyl aminothiazol-4'-yl)-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone 3a (as representative case): A mixture of *N*²-*p*-(2-anilino-

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2 AND 3a*

R	R' (m.p., °C)							
	H	<i>p</i> -MeO	<i>p</i> -EtO	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>o</i> -Me	<i>m</i> -Me	<i>p</i> -Me
Compounds 2								
Phenyl	220 ^a	196 ^o	206 ^o	199 ^o	204 ^o	218 ^c	224 ^o	212 ^b
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	204 ^d	189 ^d	193 ^d	193 ^d	196 ^d	225 ^d	221 ^d	196 ^d
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	182 ^b	185 ^b	189 ^a	209 ^a	194 ^b	177 ^b	181 ^b	171 ^b
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	203 ^b	186 ^a	192 ^b	214 ^a	199 ^b	192 ^a	189 ^a	202 ^a
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	218 ^d	204 ^d	203 ^d	197 ^d	206 ^d	211 ^d	171 ^d	194 ^d
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	202 ^d	195 ^d	188 ^d	197 ^d	193 ^d	225 ^d	221 ^d	206 ^d
2'-Pyridyl	254 ^b	233 ^b	236 ^b	229 ^b	242 ^b	244 ^b	251 ^b	241 ^b
Compounds 3a								
Phenyl	159 ^a	119 ^a	146 ^a	147 ^a	154 ^a	125 ^a	145 ^a	151 ^a
<i>p</i> -Methylphenyl	185 ^o	127 ^e	113 ^e	126 ^e	157 ^e	133 ^e	140 ^e	154 ^e
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	166 ^e	131 ^e	137 ^e	141 ^e	132 ^e	139 ^e	147 ^e	142 ^e
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	113 ^e	109 ^e	184 ^e	182 ^e	192 ^e	159 ^e	147 ^e	181 ^e
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl	181 ^e	176 ^e	168 ^e	192 ^e	185 ^e	171 ^e	167 ^e	178 ^e
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl	176 ^a	167 ^a	162 ^a	164 ^a	180 ^a	155 ^a	171 ^a	177 ^a
2'-Pyridyl	240 ^a	172 ^a	130 ^a	112 ^a	149 ^a	110 ^a	140 ^a	127 ^a

*All compounds gave satisfactory nitrogen analysis and were obtained in 60-75% yields. Recrystallised from ^aethanol, ^bmethanol, ^cAcOH, ^daqueous AcOH, and ^eaqueous ethanol.

thiazol-4'-yl)phenyl-*N*^a-phenylthiocarbamide (0.01 mol, 4.0 g), chloroacetic acid (0.012 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.012 mol) in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 5 h, during which it gave a clear solution. After cooling, the solution was poured into cold water. The solid was filtered and washed with water. It was crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 159° (Found: C, 64.79; H, 4.13; N, 12.58; S, 14.59. C₂₄H₁₈N₄OS₂ requires C, 65.16; H, 4.07; N, 12.67; S, 14.48%); ν_{max} 1670 (tert. amide), 1610 (imino), 3220 (NH

stretching), 1570 cm⁻¹ (NH bending) and characteristic absorptions of thiazole nucleus; δ (CDCl₃) 3.7 (2H, s, S—CH₂—C=O), 7.28-8.54 (15H, m, Ar) and 9.4 (1H, s, NH); *m/e* 442 (M⁺).

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References

1. R. A. MANE and D. B. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 22, 81.
2. R. A. MANE and D. B. INGLE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1983, 22, 690.
3. G. R. NEWKONE and A. NAYAK, *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1979, 25, 83.
4. V. H. PATIL and D. B. INGLE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 1000.
5. T. E. ACHARYA, P. N. DHAL and J. VIHAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1204.

Synthesis of Biflavonoids. Part-II, Oxidative Coupling of Phenolic Ketones with FeCl₃-DMF: Proof for Inter-flavonyl Linkage

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R = Ph, C₆H₄Me-*p*, C₆H₄Cl-*p*, C₆H₄Br-*p*, C₆H₄OMe-*p*, C₆H₄OEt-*p*, 2-Py;
R' = H, *p*-OMe, *p*-OEt, *p*-Br, *p*-Cl, *o*-Me, *m*-Me, *p*-Me.

OXIDATION of phloracetophenone dimethyl ether (1) was reported earlier¹ to yield 5,5'-linked dimer 2. The proof for its linkage was furnished by its conversion to hexa-*O*-methyl-6,6''-biapi-genin^{1,2}, differing from the common 8,8''-linked